

August 2019

Automate Cloud Infrastructure Deployment for Oracle Cloud and Openstack

AUTHOR:

Priyanshu Khandelwal

SUPERVISOR(S):

Antonio Nappi

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1. Abstract

This project is a part of CERN's Database Applications and Reporting Services section (IT-DB-DAR). The section provides hosting for critical engineering, administration and IT services. It builds and maintains platforms for -

- CERN developed Java applications based on application servers.
- Commercial software deployments supporting finance.
- Oracle Web Hosting.

There is ongoing work to migrate the hosting infrastructure from virtual machines to Kubernetes. Profiting of Kubernetes portability to evaluate how CERN's services can run on public clouds - in particular, on Oracle cloud.

The goals of this project are as follows -

1. Automate the process of cloud infrastructure deployment -

The existing process of deploying any infrastructure component on public/private cloud is entirely manual. Deploying any infrastructure on public cloud involves setting up virtual machines, downloading the dependencies and manual configuration of the machine. Further, to make any changes user has to SSH into the system every time. This entire process of creating deployments need to be automated.

This involves automating the deployment of the cloud infrastructure (discussed in Section 4.1) on Oracle Cloud and the deployment of Magnum cluster and cluster templates on Openstack(discussed in Section 4.2).

2. Unify the way infrastructure is deployed on public/private clouds -

There should be a common/generic procedure that can be followed to deploy infrastructure to public/private clouds.

3. Facilitate Disaster recovery for the cloud infrastructure -

CERN has numerous critical applications running on application servers. An Infrastructure crash or system crash can lead to critical data loss. Therefore, in case of any disaster, it should be possible to recover the entire infrastructure from another place.

2. BACKGROUND

As mentioned before, we are working on deploying infrastructure and automating this process of deployment on public/private clouds. Below are the details of the cloud computing platforms Oracle Cloud and Openstack and the infrastructure that we are deploying on each of them.

2.1. Oracle Cloud

2.1.1. Overview

Oracle Cloud is a “cloud computing service offered by Oracle Corporation providing servers, storage, network, applications and services through a global network of Oracle Corporation managed data centers” [7.1].

Oracle Cloud Infrastructure (OCI) comprises of infrastructure components that can be created on Oracle Cloud and used for computation and storage.

2.1.2. The infrastructure to be deployed

The infrastructure that is targeted to be deployed on Oracle Cloud is shown in Figure 1. It comprises of the following five components -

- a. **Kubernetes Cluster** - A cluster of nodes running Kubernetes, which is an open source container orchestration tool for automating deployment and management of containerized applications.
- b. **Elasticsearch Instance** - Elasticsearch is a distributed, RESTful search and analytics engine.
- c. **InfluxDb Instance** - A time series database for monitoring metrics and events.
- d. **Kibana Instance** - Provide visualizations for the Elasticsearch data.
- e. **Grafana Instance** - Provides analytics and monitoring features for InfluxDb.

Figure 1. *The Infrastructure to be deployed on Oracle Cloud*

Kubernetes cluster hosts various applications. The log data that is generated from the cluster is stored in Elasticsearch. Elasticsearch is connected to a Kibana instance that helps in analysis of the data through interactive visualizations. The time series metric data that is generated from the cluster is stored in InfluxDb. This is connected to a Grafana instance that provide visualization for this data.

2.2. Openstack

2.2.1. Overview of Openstack

Openstack is an “open source Cloud Computing platform that is easy to use, simple to implement, interoperable between deployments, works well at all scales, and meets the needs of users and operators of both public and private clouds” [7.3].

Openstack is used by CERN in production to cater to the high performance computing and storage needs of high energy physics experiments running at CERN like the Large Hadron Collider etc which generates huge amounts of data.

2.2.2. Overview of Openstack Magnum

Openstack Magnum is an API provided by Openstack to interact with container orchestration systems like Kubernetes.

This project involves creation of Kubernetes cluster on Openstack using Openstack Magnum. This is a two step process, which involves creation of Magnum cluster template and then the creation of Kubernetes cluster.

- a. **Magnum cluster template** - It is a template that comprise of a set of parameters that are used to create a cluster of common container orchestrators. A template can be used to create multiple clusters.

- b. **Magnum Cluster** - This comprises of a bunch of containers (nodes) that can host applications. The parameters of the cluster is defined by it's cluster template. Magnum deploys the Cluster template resulting in creation of the cluster's infrastructure on Openstack.

3. PROPOSED SOLUTION

We explored an open source tool developed by Hashicorp, called **Terraform**, which can create and manage cloud infrastructure safely. It works on a plugin based system. All major cloud providers have Terraform plugins available so Terraform can be used to deploy infrastructure on any of these cloud providers. Terraform uses Hashicorp's Configuration Language (HCL) for configuration.

Deploying any type of infrastructure with Terraform is a three step process.

a. Writing Infrastructure as Code -

The entire infrastructure of any cloud provider can be coded in a set of declarative, configuration files. This includes low-level components such as compute instances, storage, and networking, as well as high-level components such as DNS entries, SaaS features, etc.

b. Analyzing Execution Plan -

Terraform provides a deployment plan for the current set of configuration. This deployment plan describes the details of every infrastructure component that will be created, changed or deleted if you apply this plan. Terraform identifies the dependencies between the infrastructure components and builds an efficient plan to deploy it. This helps in identifying errors in the configuration which can be corrected by just changing the current configuration.

c. Applying Changes -

After analyzing the deployment plan, user can proceed with the deployment of the coded infrastructure. Terraform interacts with the cloud provider and deploys the infrastructure itself.

Image Credit: <https://www.terraform.io/>

Figure 3. *Terraform workflow*

3.1 Creating a module in Terraform

For creating a module in Terraform, a set of configuration files need to be coded in HCL (Hashicorp Configuration Language). These terraform files declares certain resources (infrastructural objects) which are later provisioned on the remote cloud.. The configuration files needed to create a virtual machine on Oracle Cloud and deploying Elasticsearch on it are described below. The process of creating modules in Terraform to deploy other kinds of services like Kibana, Grafana, Kubernetes Cluster etc on remote cloud is quite similar. We are following the principle of 'separation of concerns' so every terraform file (.tf extension) would handle the responsibility to perform one type of task.

1. `terraform.tfvars.example` - This file is a template that lists all the keys and secret variables whose values need to be provided. User needs to create `terraform.tfvars` locally and provide the value for all these variables or else the module would ask for these values to be provided as input through stdin when the module is executed.
2. `provider.tf` - The keys and oracle cloud id(s) necessary for oracle cloud authentication need to be specified here for instance, `tenant_ocid`, `user_ocid`, `fingerprint`, `private_key_path` (for SSH) and `region`. We are not storing the important keys and secrets in `provider.tf` instead we can create variables which takes these values from `terraform.tfvars`.
3. `variables.tf` - All the variables used in any files need to be listed here.

4. `network.tf` - The resources that create the various components of the network layer of our infrastructure are to be specified here. We are creating the following resources -
 - a. `oci_core_virtual_network` - This is the resource type for the virtual network block resource.
 - b. `oci_core_subnet` - This is the resource type for the network subnet.
 - c. `oci_core_internet_gateway` - This is the resource type for internet gateway.
 - d. `oci_core_route_table` - This is the resource type for routing table and comprises of the routing rules.
5. `security-lists.tf` - The resource for creating a security list for our network is to be specified here. Security lists comprise of ingress and egress security rules and it controls the type of traffic in our network.
6. `elk.sh` - This is a bash script that will be executed on the remote virtual machine after it is created. We need to specify commands to setup firewall rules, download and install elasticsearch binaries and start elasticsearch daemon.
7. `elasticsearch.tf` - This is the main file for the module. We need to specify the resource of type `oci_core_instance`. It would create a virtual machine which will run elasticsearch. This resource has attributes for customizing the instance, virtual network interface card, ssh access etc.

3.2 Deploying Infrastructure with Terraform

The following instructions are tested for Ubuntu 18.04 LTS. The process to deploy any terraform module for Oracle Cloud or Openstack is similar and is described below -

1. Copy the file `terraform.tfvars.example` to create another file `terraform.tfvars` and fill in the values of the various parameters in the file `terraform.tfvars` and fill in the value of the parameters mentioned in the file or else the default value will be used.

```
cp terraform.tfvars.example terraform.tfvars
```

`terraform.tfvars` is a file that contains client secrets, keys (or path to keys) and other configuration specific parameters like number of node instances, desired version of various softwares, type of virtual machine, path to files that you want to transfer from your local system to virtual machines etc.

2. Then we initialize the directory which contains the terraform module. This makes the module aware of the cloud provider and download the required cloud specific plugins automatically. You can do this by running:

```
terraform init
```

3. Analyze the simplified deployment plan generated by Terraform describing changes that are going to take place if this configuration is deployed.

```
terraform plan
```

4. After the plan is confirmed, the deployment process can be initiated by running:

```
terraform apply
```

After the infrastructure is deployed, terraform module will output certain parameters for the deployment(mentioned in `output.tf` file) like IP address of the virtual machine that is created on cloud etc which are useful for connecting to the remote infrastructure and managing it. These output parameters can be modified by changing the configuration of the file `output.tf`.

3.2. Modifying the existing cloud infrastructure

Once the infrastructure is deployed on cloud using Terraform there can be need to add, modify or delete the infrastructure. It is possible to do so using Terraform in just a few steps -

a. Adding or Modifying the existing configuration -

i. Change the configuration files

ii. Generate a deployment plan for the changed infrastructure by running the following command. Terraform will describe what new components will be added or removed along with existing components.

```
terraform plan
```

iii. Initiate the deployment by running

```
terraform apply
```

b. Deleting the infrastructure -

For destroying the deployment and deleting all the allocated resources by terraform, run the following command -

```
terraform destroy
```


4. Project Outcomes

4.1. Terraform modules for Oracle Cloud

We used Terraform to build modules that are capable of deploying and managing the infrastructure that is discussed in Section 2 Figure 2. We created 4 Terraform modules that can deploy these different components of the infrastructure on Oracle Cloud -

4.1.1. Kubernetes Cluster

This module creates a Kubernetes cluster on Oracle cloud. The user can specify OCI configuration parameters, identity and access parameters, client SSH keys, virtual machine configuration, network gateways, virtual network, subnets, nodepool configuration and helm, calico versions to install on the VM.

4.1.2. Elasticsearch and Kibana

Provisions a virtual machine and deploy Elasticsearch with Kibana. The user can specify OCI configuration parameters, identity and access parameters, client SSH keys, Elasticsearch and Kibana versions to install on the VM.

4.1.3. InfluxDb

Provisions a virtual machine and deploys InfluxDb. The user can specify OCI configuration parameters, identity and access parameters, client SSH keys, InfluxDb version to install on the VM, username and password for InfluxDb user and copy configuration files from local system to the remote virtual machine.

4.1.4. Grafana

Provisions a virtual machine and deploys Grafana. The user can specify OCI configuration parameters, identity and access parameters, client SSH keys, Grafana version to install on the VM, username and password for Grafana user and copy configuration files from local system to the remote virtual machine.

4.2. Terraform modules for Openstack

We used Terraform to build modules that are capable of deploying and managing the infrastructure that is discussed in section 2 Figure 2 on Openstack. Terraform modules that can deploy/create the following were developed as part of this project -

4.2.1 Kubernetes Cluster

This module creates a Kubernetes cluster on Openstack through Openstack Magnum. The user can choose from available Magnum cluster template to build a cluster from it. The user can specify openstack configuration parameters, identity and access parameters, client SSH keys, master and worker nodes parameters and virtual machine configuration.

4.2.2 Magnum Cluster Template

This module creates a Magnum cluster template on Openstack through Openstack Magnum. The user can add new labels for the template, change or delete the existing labels in the template. The user can specify openstack configuration parameters, identity and access parameters, client SSH keys, network/volume drivers and other network parameters, docker storage driver, docker volume size, master and worker nodes parameters and virtual machine configuration.

5. Conclusion

We were able to automate and simplify the entire process of infrastructural setup. The need to manually set up the system along with the dependencies is eliminated, user don't have to write long complex queries for deployment everytime instead the user just need to run a couple of short terraform commands to deploy a particular set of configuration of the infrastructure specified in code files in the terraform module.

The deployments are Cloud Agnostic as we use the same procedure of deployment for different cloud providers like Oracle Cloud and Openstack.

Now, we can not only create the infrastructure but also make changes in it, improve it or destroy it easily with Terraform. Even if the infrastructure crashes, it can be redeployed from the previous active state. In a nutshell, we were able to achieve the project targets.

6. Future Scope

The codebase developed in this project comprises of different components, each of which can deploy one type of service on cloud. For eg, there is a separate module to deploy Elasticsearch and a different module to deploy InfluxDb on Oracle Cloud. These different components can be clubbed together as different siblings modules, all under one parent terraform module. This would create lightweight abstractions, so that we can describe our infrastructure in terms of its architecture, rather than directly in terms of physical objects.

The Terraform modules developed in this project store the state of the infrastructure when it was deployed, on the local system of client. But when multiple developers work on the same infrastructure, the state of the infrastructure would change which would create different aged states in different local systems. So there is a need for collaborative development of infrastructural states.

7. References

- 7.1. <https://openlab.cern/project/oracle-weblogic-kubernetes>
- 7.2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oracle_Cloud
- 7.3 <https://docs.openstack.org/project-team-guide/introduction.html>
- 7.4. <https://www.terraform.io>

